

How the Abstract Becomes Concrete:

Irrational Numbers Are Anchored on Natural Numbers and Perfect Squares

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Abstract

Mathematical cognition research has largely emphasized concepts that can be directly perceived or grounded in visuospatial referents. These include concrete number systems like natural numbers, integers, and rational numbers. Here, we investigate how a more abstract number system, the irrationals denoted by radical expressions like $\sqrt{2}$, is understood across three tasks. Performance on a magnitude comparison task suggests that people interpret irrational numbers – specifically, the radicands of radical expressions – as natural numbers. Response times and strategy self-reports during number line estimation reveal that the spatial locations of irrationals are determined by anchoring to neighboring perfect squares. Perfect squares also facilitate the evaluation of complex arithmetic expressions. These converging results align with a constellation of related anchoring phenomena spanning tasks and number systems of varying complexity. Accordingly, we propose that the task-specific recruitment of more concrete representations, *formal anchoring*, is an important mechanism for understanding and teaching mathematics.

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The historical development of number systems can be characterized as a gradual progression from the concrete to the abstract. Natural numbers, which denote the cardinalities of sets, were understood directly and formalized first. According to the mathematician Leopold Kronecker, “God created” this relatively concrete number system, whereas more abstract number systems like the integers, rationals, irrationals, and reals are “the work of man.” In contrast, cognitive science research emphasizes how number systems are grounded in analog magnitude representations (Moyer & Landauer, 1967). The natural numbers are thought to be grounded in directly perceptible objects and are internally represented as continuous magnitudes on a mental number line. For more abstract number systems, the necessity of mastering the associated symbol systems has been acknowledged. However, the focus is often on how these symbol systems recruit and restructure magnitude representations. Examples include incorporating the inverse relationship between positive and negative integers into the mental number line and capturing the ratio relationship between the numerators and denominators of fractions more precisely (Matthews & Chesney, 2015; Varma & Schwartz, 2011).

Comparatively little attention has been directed towards abstract mathematical concepts that are both imperceptible and incapable of being fully grounded in visuospatial referents. For such concepts, do magnitude representations continue to be heavily recruited or does notation-specific strategic processing become more essential? In this paper, we use irrational numbers as a test case to address this question. To our knowledge, this is the first study to explore how familiar irrational numbers denoted by symbolic radical expressions like $\sqrt{2}$ are mentally represented and processed by typical adults. Our study has implications for extending theories of

numerical cognition and for instructional design in mathematics education. It builds on literature concerned with how people understand natural numbers, integers, and rational numbers.

Natural Numbers

The natural numbers are the set of countable numbers.¹ Their mental representation has been studied extensively using the *magnitude comparison* (MC) task. When comparing which number in a pair is greater or lesser, response time decreases as the difference between the numbers increases (Moyer & Landauer, 1967). For instance, people can judge the greater or lesser number in the pair (2, 9) more quickly than in the pair (5, 6). This well-replicated performance pattern is known as the *distance effect*. It manifests whether participants compare symbolic numbers or visuospatial numerosities like sets of dots (Buckley & Gillman, 1974). The distance effect is commonly interpreted as evidence that natural numbers are represented in part as psychophysically scaled magnitudes. It has been observed as early as infancy with numerosities (Xu & Spelke, 2000) and kindergarten with symbolic numbers (Sekuler & Mierkiewicz, 1977). Over development, children's representation of numerical magnitude changes such that response times decrease overall and the slope of the distance effect decreases (Sekuler & Mierkiewicz, 1977). These changes indicate improved precision of magnitude representations.

The magnitude representation of natural numbers and its development have also been probed by the *number line estimation* (NLE) task. In the bounded version of this task, participants are presented with a number line labeled zero at the left endpoint and ten at the right endpoint (Cohen & Blanc-Goldhammer, 2012). The middle segment is left blank. Numbers are presented sequentially and participants are prompted to map their positions to the line by

¹ Some definitions include zero within the set of natural numbers, though others do not.

marking on paper or clicking on a virtual number line with a computer mouse. Performance is typically measured by average absolute error – the absolute difference between the correct position of the number and the position selected by the participant. Higher error values indicate worse performance. Over development, children’s accuracy on NLE tasks improves gradually (Fazio, Bailey, Thompson, & Siegler, 2014). More specifically, their estimation patterns suggest that natural numbers are initially represented in a compressed, logarithmically spaced fashion. This incorrect representation is revised later by spacing the same numerical magnitudes more linearly. Performance gains on these tasks are driven in part by anchoring estimates to number lines’ midpoints and endpoints (Ashcraft & Moore, 2012; Barth & Paladino, 2011; Opfer et al., 2016; Siegler & Thompson, 2014).

Individual differences in the magnitude representations of natural numbers, as indexed by the slope of the distance effect in the MC task, predict variation in mathematical achievement for elementary (De Smedt, Verschaffel, & Ghesquière, 2009) and middle school students (Halberda, Mazocco, & Feigenson, 2008). Likewise, NLE performance predicts mathematical achievement in elementary school students, although not older students learning more advanced topics (Sasanguie, De Smedt, Defever, & Reynvoet, 2012). Instructional studies support a causal link between numerical magnitude representations and arithmetic skills. Young children who were tutored on the magnitudes of small natural numbers via a board game performed better on simple arithmetic problems than their peers who received a control lesson (Siegler & Ramani, 2009).

Integers

The natural numbers combined with their additive inverses, the negative numbers, form the integers $\{\dots, -2, -1, 0, 1, 2, \dots\}$. Comprehending the meaning of this number system requires engaging in additional symbolic processing. For instance, when judging the greater number in

the pair $(-3, -9)$, it is necessary to inhibit the whole number interpretations of “-3” as “3” and “-9” as “9”. Children initially compare such integer pairs by using a symbolic strategy. First, they convert the negative numbers to natural numbers by ignoring the minus signs. Next, they compare the numerical magnitudes and then reverse this judgment (Varma & Schwartz, 2011). This strategy results in a distance effect when comparing pairs of negatives numbers. But when comparing mixed integer pairs like $(-4, 9)$, judgments can be made by noticing that positives are greater than negatives. The result is the absence of a distance effect in elementary school children. Over development, this strategic processing of integers is substituted by accessing a restructured magnitude representation that incorporates the symmetry of positives and negatives around the anchor zero. Adults represent the negative number line as a reflection of the positive number line, incorporating the additive inverse property . This shift manifests as an *inverse distance effect* when comparing mixed integer pairs – as the distance between the integers increases, so does the responses time.

As with natural numbers, NLE tasks have also uncovered a logarithmic-to-linear shift in the mental representation of integers. When estimating the positions of positive numbers in the range $0 - 1,000$ and negative numbers in the range $-1,000 - 0$, second graders exhibit logarithmic magnitude representations. By contrast, fourth and sixth graders exhibit linear representations for both ranges (Brez, Miller, & Ramirez, 2015). This logarithmic-to-linear shift extends to larger number ranges and older people. Middle school students’ estimates of integers in the negative range $-10,000 - 0$ and the combined range $-1,000 - 1,000$ are linear, though with lower accuracy for negative numbers (Young & Booth, 2015). Performance on NLE tasks like these depends partly on recognizing the symmetry of the integers around the zero anchor (Saxe, Earnest, Sitabkhan, Haldar, Lewis, & Zheng, 2010; Tsang, Blair, Bofferding, & Schwartz, 2015). These

studies inspired the design of a manipulative that encourages learners to incorporate the zero anchor in their magnitude representation of the integers. Doing so improves arithmetic problem-solving on difficult items like (Tsang et al., 2015).

Rational Numbers

Rational numbers are the set of numbers that can be written as a ratio of two integers such that the denominator is non-zero. Magnitude comparison with symbolic fractions and decimals, as well as with non-symbolic ratios, produces the distance effect (DeWolf, Grounds, Bassok, & Holyoak, 2014; Matthews & Chesney, 2015; Matthews & Lewis, 2016; Siegler, Thompson, & Schneider, 2011; Varma & Karl, 2013). Thus, rational numbers are also thought to be integrated on the mental number line. As learners begin to understand fraction magnitudes, the slope of the distance effect is nearly zero. With time, fraction magnitude information becomes more accessible and the slope increases gradually. By adulthood, the slope stabilizes (Gabriel, Szucs, & Content, 2013). These behavioral changes are paralleled by the discovery and use of strategies to facilitate performance. For instance, children and young adults often report using unit fractions like $\frac{1}{2}$ as anchors to perform fraction magnitude comparison (Fazio, Dewolf, & Siegler, 2016; Siegler & Thompson, 2014).

In contrast to natural numbers and integers, NLE tasks suggest that the representation of rational numbers does not undergo a logarithmic-to-linear developmental shift. When children and adults perform NLE with decimal proportions, they both exhibit highly linear estimation patterns (Iuculano & Butterworth, 2011). However, estimates do become more accurate in the 0 – 1 and 0 – 5 ranges. These performance gains may result partly from using unit fractions like $\frac{1}{2}$ as anchors (Siegler & Thompson, 2014; Spinillo & Bryant, 1991).

The precision of rational number magnitude representations is also associated with higher-level mathematical skills. Symbolic fraction magnitude representations predict achievement across a range of domains and measures – fraction arithmetic, algebra, grade school standardized exams, and high school mathematical achievement (Siegler et al., 2012). Similarly, accuracy on NLE tasks using decimals predicts mathematics achievement in elementary school students (Schneider, Grabner, Zurich, & Paetsch, 2009). Even nonsymbolic ratio precision predicts college students' knowledge of fractions and algebra (Matthews, Lewis, & Hubbard, 2016). Causal support for the link between magnitude knowledge and arithmetic skills comes from interventions that devote more instructional time to mastering the magnitudes of fractions. Results show that emphasizing magnitude boosts arithmetic skills for high and low achievers (Fuchs et al., 2013).

Irrational Numbers

Irrational numbers are incommensurable. Unlike rational numbers, they cannot be expressed as ratios of integers such that the denominator is non-zero. Their decimal expansions are infinitely long, non-repeating, and ostensibly random. When they were first proposed, the notion seemed outlandish. According to a famous anecdote that originates with Vitruvius, the Greek mathematician who first proved their existence was drowned at sea for challenging the ratio doctrine of numbers. It was not until the late 1800s that irrationals were formalized and properly integrated onto the real number line (Dedekind, 1963). Two subclasses can be distinguished – algebraic irrationals and transcendental numbers. Algebraic irrationals are the solutions to polynomial equations and can be denoted by expressions of the form $a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + \dots + a_nx^n = 0$. Transcendental numbers, which are not the solutions to any polynomial equations, include e and π .

Just one other study has investigated the cognitive bases of algebraic irrationals. It explored whether the same human “number sense” that allows us to compare the magnitudes of natural numbers, integers, and rational numbers extends to irrationals (Obersteiner & Hofreiter, 2017). Participants performed magnitude comparisons with irrationals of the form \sqrt{y} . Both the root y and the radicand x could vary. The authors tested whether participants compared the magnitudes of irrationals by accessing their holistic magnitudes or by focusing on the root and radicand components. Comparisons were faster when both numbers contained a common root component, as in the pairs $(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{8})$. Likewise, comparisons were faster when both numbers contained a common radicand component, as in the pair $(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{18})$. When both the roots and radicands differed, as in the pair $(\sqrt{2}, \sqrt{18})$, response times were slow. Unexpectedly, response times for the common component pairs were not predicted by the distances between the root components or radicand components. These mixed results require explanation. One problem is the use of unfamiliar irrational numbers. Another is the highly expert sample of mathematics graduate students and professors. Therefore, it is unclear how typical adults understand familiar irrational numbers like $\sqrt{2}$.

In our study, we focus on algebraic irrationals. Our stimuli are familiar square root expressions of the form \sqrt{x} . These expressions denote irrational numbers when the radicand x is not a perfect square (e.g., $\sqrt{2}$) and natural numbers when the radicand is a perfect square (e.g., $\sqrt{4}$). In the following sections, we will collectively refer to these as *radical expressions* because both contain the radical sign.

Research Questions and Hypotheses

First, we asked whether radical expressions are represented like natural numbers, integers, and rational numbers – as continuous magnitudes integrated on the mental number line. We refer to this proposal as the *mental number line hypothesis*. An alternative proposal is that

people use processes that capitalize on the structure of radical expressions. For instance, when judging the greater or lesser number in the pair $(\sqrt{3}, \sqrt{8})$, people may ignore the radical signs and only compare the radicand components (3, 8) using their magnitude representations of natural numbers. This is possible because when x and y are non-negative, judgments of (\sqrt{x}, \sqrt{y}) and (x, y) are equivalent. We refer to this as the *equivalence strategy hypothesis*.

Second, we investigated whether people process irrational numbers by strategically anchoring them on more concrete concepts like natural numbers and perfect squares. Specifically, we hypothesized the possible use of a *multiplication strategy* on the MC task whereby perfect square pairs like $(\sqrt{4}, \sqrt{9})$ are transformed to computationally analogous “tie” multiplication problems like $2 \times 3 = 6$. Such a transformation might facilitate comparison because tie problems are processed more quickly than non-tie problems of comparable size (Ashcraft, 1992; Parkman, 1972). On the NLE task, irrational numbers might be estimated in relation to perfect squares – the *landmark strategy*. For example, people may estimate the positions of irrational numbers like $\sqrt{10}$ by referencing the positions of neighboring perfect squares like 9 and 16. Finally, people may leverage their knowledge of perfect squares during arithmetic problem-solving. When simplifying $\sqrt{12}$, a naïve strategy would be to decompose the radicand into its prime factors and then shift pairs of common factors outside the radical sign – the *prime factorization strategy*. Consider the following solution procedure:

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A more efficient approach is to decompose the radicand into its perfect square factors – the *perfect squares factorization strategy*:

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Third, we investigated whether individual differences in the mental representation and processing of irrationals explain variation in conceptual and procedural knowledge of this number system. Some researchers have proposed that magnitude knowledge is at the core of numerical and arithmetic learning (Link, Nuerk, & Moeller, 2014; Siegler, 2016). Contra this view, we hypothesize that the influence of magnitude representations on arithmetic problem-solving attenuates as the abstraction of number systems increases. Arithmetic expertise with irrationals may not depend as much on magnitude knowledge.

Method

Participants

Overall, 81 undergraduate students (24 males, 57 females) from a large Midwestern university were recruited via flyers distributed across campus. Their ages ranged from 18 to 24 ($M = 20.5$ years, $SD = 1.7$). On a questionnaire, 30.3% of participants self-reported that they were enrolled in a major emphasizing quantitative and analytic skills such as science, technology, engineering, mathematics, finance, or economics. Experimental sessions spanned about 60 minutes and all participants received \$12 in compensation. The protocol was approved by the local Institutional Review Board.

Design

We employed a within-subjects experimental design, with each participant completing all levels of the four experimental tasks. See Table 1 for an overview of the design and materials.

Table 1. Overview of the design and materials used in this study.

Task	Condition	Stimuli	Dependent Variables
Magnitude	natural numbers	0, 1, 2..., 9	accuracy

comparison (MC)	one-digit radicals	, , , ,	response time
Number line estimation (NLE)	natural numbers	1, 2, 3, ..., 9	absolute error response time R^2 value
	one-digit radicals	, , ,	
	perfect squares	, , ,	
Strategy questionnaire	two-digit radicals	, , ,	strategy type
	natural numbers	How did you place 7?	
	one-digit radicals	How did you place ?	
	perfect squares	How did you place ?	
Irrationals knowledge test	two-digit radicals	How did you place ?	accuracy strategy type
	number classification	Is rational or irrational?	
	density knowledge	How many irrationals are between 0 – 1?	
	operation concepts	The sum of a rational and an irrational is ...?	
	simple arithmetic	Simplify .	
	complex arithmetic	Simplify .	

Note. The stimuli for the strategy questionnaire and the irrationals knowledge test are examples from the larger set of items.

Magnitude comparison task. The first task was magnitude comparison and its stimuli were defined by four variables – type, distance, size, and perfect square status. The type variable refers to whether a number pair consisted of natural numbers or radical expressions. For the distance and size variables, we used two definitions to evaluate the equivalence strategy and mental number line hypotheses (research question 1). The distance variable was the absolute difference between the numbers. The first definition of distance focused on the radicand components. For example, the distance of the pair (,) was . The second definition focused on the actual magnitude values of the radical expressions. For example, the distance of the pair (,) was . The size variable was defined as the average of the two numbers. The first definition again used the radicand components. For example, the size of the pair (,) was . The second definition again

used the actual magnitude values of the radical expressions. For example, the size of the pair $(,)$ was . The perfect square variable was defined by whether both natural numbers or radicands were perfect squares like $(4, 9)$ or $(,)$. Two dependent variables, accuracy and response time (RT) in milliseconds, were collected.

Number line estimation task. The second task was number line estimation (NLE) and it included one within-subjects variable (type) with four levels – natural numbers, one-digit radicals, perfect square radicals, and two-digit radicals. The natural numbers were 0, 1, 2, 3, ..., 10; the one-digit radicals were ; the perfect square radicals were ; and the two-digit radicals were . In each level, the first and last values served as manipulation checks. Data associated with these values were not included in the main analyses. Three dependent variables were formed – average absolute error, response times, and linearity of estimates. Average absolute error was the absolute difference between a participant's selected position and the target position. Response times were measured in milliseconds. Linearity of estimates was the relationship between participants' selected positions and target positions as estimated by linear regression (R^2).

Strategy questionnaire. The third task was the strategy questionnaire for the NLE task. The independent variable was number type and the dependent variable was self-reported estimation strategies.

Irrationals knowledge test. The fourth task was the irrationals knowledge test. It consisted of five subsections that were collapsed to form two independent variables – conceptual knowledge and procedural knowledge. Two dependent variables were computed – accuracy on each section and problem-solving strategies on the complex arithmetic subsection.

Materials

All experimental materials are available via the Open Science Framework

(<https://osf.io/6s9pc/#>).

Magnitude comparison task. To investigate the magnitude representations of radical expressions, we created two sets of number pairs. The first set included natural number pairs formed from the combinations of 0, 1, 2, ..., 9, with same-number pairs excluded (90 pairs). We were particularly interested in pairs where both numbers were perfect squares, like (4, 9) or (1, 1). Hence, we included an additional copy of each of the 12 perfect square pairs in the stimulus set. In total, 102 natural number pairs were used in blocks 1 and 2. Participants judged the greater of two numbers in the first block and the lesser in the second block. Natural number pairs were mirrored by 102 pairs of radical expressions formed in the same way from $\sqrt{0}, \sqrt{1}, \sqrt{2}, \dots, \sqrt{9}$. These pairs were used in blocks 3 and 4. Block 3 required greater judgments and block 4 required lesser judgments. Within each block, number pairs were presented in random order. Overall, there were 408 trials.

Number line estimation task. Each of the four levels of the type variable was associated with one NLE block. The first block consisted of the natural number stimuli 0, 1, 2, ..., 10. The second block consisted of the one-digit radical stimuli $\sqrt{0}, \sqrt{1}, \sqrt{2}, \dots, \sqrt{9}$. This block contained perfect squares and irrationals. The third block included perfect squares like $\sqrt{4}, \sqrt{9}, \dots$, and the fourth block included two-digit radicals from $\sqrt{10}, \sqrt{11}, \dots, \sqrt{99}$. These were all irrational numbers. Within each block, the 11 stimuli were presented in random order. Overall, there were 44 trials.

Strategy questionnaire. Strategy prompts were developed to examine reasoning during the NLE task. Participants completed an eight-item paper-and-pencil strategy questionnaire composed of two prompts for each of the four blocks – natural numbers, one-digit radicals, perfect square radicals, and two-digit radicals. All prompts were in the form “How did you

decide where to place x ?", where x was a value from one of the four blocks. See Table 1 for examples.

Irrationals knowledge test. We constructed a novel paper-and-pencil test to measure conceptual and procedural reasoning about irrational numbers. Many items were adapted from literature documenting students' misconceptions (Van Hoof et al., 2015). Correct items earned one point each; partial credit was not awarded. The conceptual items were distributed across three subsections. They required participants to (1) classify numbers like $\sqrt{2}$ as either rational or irrational, (2) answer questions about the density of rational and irrational numbers, and (3) reason about the results of arithmetic operations on rational and irrational numbers. Most of these items were in the selected response format. The procedural items were distributed over two subsections. Subsection (4) required simplifying radical expressions and subsection (5) required performing arithmetic operations on multiple radical expressions. These were all fill-in-the-blank items. Example items from all five subsections are in Table 1.

Procedure

After obtaining informed written consent, participants were seated alone in a quiet laboratory room in front of a Windows PC with an extended keyboard, a mouse, and a monitor measuring 55.6 cm diagonally.

Magnitude comparison task. Participants first completed the MC task, implemented in the experimental design program OpenSesame 2.9.5 (Mathôt, Schreij, & Theeuwes, 2012). All number pairs were shown in white text against a black background. Each trial began with a blank screen for 250 ms, after which a fixation dot was shown in the center of the screen for 1000 milliseconds, followed by a blank screen for 500 milliseconds. A number pair was presented next, with each number offset about 5 centimeters on either side of the center. All numbers were

displayed in the font Cambria Math (point 80). Participants indicated the larger or smaller number by pressing the key below the target number – “Z” for the number on the left and “M” for the number on the right. The stimuli were visible until participants made a response. Correct responses were followed by *Correct* in green text and incorrect responses by *Incorrect* in red text. This feedback was displayed for 500 milliseconds. Participants required about 6 minutes to complete each of the four blocks.

Number line estimation task and strategy questionnaire. Next, participants completed the NLE task written in JavaScript and hosted online (www.psycholab.org/FreeLab). They were instructed to be as accurate as possible and that speed was irrelevant. On each trial, a natural number or radical expression was shown above a number line. The number line was only labeled at the endpoints, zero on the left and ten on the right. The middle was left blank. Participants estimated the number’s position on the line by left-clicking with a computer mouse. To prevent them from rushing through the task, a blank screen was shown for three seconds between trials and clicks during this interval were ignored. Feedback was not provided. Overall, participants needed about six minutes to complete this task. Afterward, they were given the strategy questionnaire to complete at their own pace.

Irrationals knowledge test. Finally, participants completed the irrationals knowledge test without feedback or the use of electronic devices. Approximately 25 minutes were allotted to respond.

Afterward, demographic information was collected, participants were debriefed, and compensated with \$12 in cash.

Results

Magnitude Comparison Task

The average accuracy across magnitude comparison blocks was high (98.2%). To determine whether there was a speed-accuracy tradeoff, we correlated the average response times and average accuracy of all participants. These variables were not significantly correlated ($r = -.079$, $p = .486$). Because of the ceiling effect in accuracy and the lack of a speed-accuracy tradeoff, subsequent analyses concentrated on the response time data only. We trimmed all trials on which participants made an incorrect response. This was 1.8% of the overall data. Following common practice in the literature, we also trimmed response times outside of the interval 200-2000 ms (Varma & Karl, 2013). This was a further 2.6% of the overall data.

Recall that the first research question asks whether the magnitudes of radical expressions are compared by referencing a mental number line or by using the equivalence strategy. The second research question, concerning the use of anchoring strategies, is also relevant here for answering whether perfect square radicals like $(\)$ are processed more quickly via the multiplication strategy. Addressing these questions demanded sensitivity to the natural confound between size and perfect square status in our stimulus set. Between 0 and 10, there are three “small” perfect squares (0, 1, and 4), but only one “large” perfect square (9). Thus, the average size and distance of perfect squares pairs is smaller than that of non-perfect square pairs. To control for this confound, we used hierarchical linear regression.

We explored whether the canonical distance and size effects replicated for natural number comparisons and extended to radical expression comparisons. The size effect is the finding that, controlling for distance, numerical magnitude comparisons require more time as the operands grow larger (Parkman, 1971). For instance, the pair (2, 3) can be compared more quickly than the pair (7, 8). Additionally, we investigated whether the type of a stimulus (natural

numbers or radical expressions) and perfect square status (yes or no) affected RTs. If there is an advantage for comparing perfect squares, then it may only apply to radical expression pairs like (,), but not to natural number pairs like (1, 4). Hence, we included the interaction between type and perfect square status in the hierarchical regression analysis. The dependent variable was RT and the five predictor variables were entered sequentially: distance (1 – 9), size (0.5 – 8.5), type (natural numbers or radical expressions), perfect square status (yes or no), and the type by perfect square interaction.

We addressed the first research question in two hierarchical regression analyses. The first defined the distance and size variables by the radicand components of the radical expressions. This was consistent with the equivalence hypothesis. The second defined them by the actual magnitude values of the radical expressions. This was consistent with the mental number line hypothesis.

The final model from the first analysis, which evaluated the equivalence strategy hypothesis, is in Table 2. Distance was entered during step 1; it was a significant predictor of RT, $R^2 = .278$, $F(1, 88) = 33.9$, $p < .001$. Size was entered during step 2 and it accounted for significant additional variance, $\Delta R^2 = .183$, $R^2 = .461$, $F(1, 87) = 29.6$, $p < .001$. Thus, we replicated the distance and size effects for natural numbers and extended them to radical expressions (Fig. 1). Number type was entered during step 3; it explained the most additional variance in RTs, $\Delta R^2 = .471$, $R^2 = .932$, $F(1, 86) = 598.5$, $p < .001$. The positive β weight means that radical expressions required more time to compare than natural numbers. Perfect square status was entered during step 4; it did not explain significant additional variance in RTs, $\Delta R^2 = .001$, $R^2 = .993$, $F(1, 85) = 1.07$, $p = .303$. The interaction between number type and perfect

square value was entered during step 5; it was also a nonsignificant predictor, $\Delta R^2 = .000$, $R^2 = .993$, $F(1, 84) = .01$, $p = .935$.

Table 2. Final hierarchical linear regression models predicting RTs during magnitude comparison when distance and size were defined by (a) the radicand components and (b) the actual magnitude values of the radical expressions.

Model	Predictor	<i>Std. β</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i> ²
Equivalence Strategy	Constant		107.49	.000	.933
	Distance	-.535	-18.40	.000	
	Size	.434	15.06	.000	
	Type	.687	22.68	.000	
	Perfect Square	-.033	-.804	.424	
	Type X Perfect Square	.003	.082	.935	
Mental Number Line	Constant		43.03	.000	.838
	Distance	-.481	-8.99	.000	
	Size	.199	-3.74	.000	
	Type	.687	14.56	.000	
	Perfect Square	.024	.368	.714	
	Type X Perfect Square	-.003	-.053	.958	

XXX

Fig. 1. Distance and size effects, defined by the radicands and consistent with the equivalence strategy hypothesis, were found for natural number and radical expression magnitude comparisons. Shaded regions are 95% confidence envelopes.

To summarize, the first regression analysis defined the distance and size variables by the radicand components of radical expressions. The distance, size, and type effects were observed. In the second regression analysis, the distance and size variables were defined by the actual magnitude values of the radical expressions. The same three effects were observed (Table 2). Critically, the first analysis explained more of the variance in RTs than the second analysis

(93.3% versus 83.8%). Thus, these findings favor the equivalence strategy hypothesis over the mental number line hypothesis. Radical expressions like $(\sqrt{\quad}, \sqrt{\quad})$ appear to be converted to natural numbers like $(8, 8)$ and then compared using the mental number line.

Recall that the second research question asked whether people strategically anchor abstract irrational numbers on concrete natural numbers and perfect squares. The regression model favoring the equivalence strategy supports the idea that natural numbers are used as anchors. Moreover, both regression models indicate that perfect squares are not used as anchors – perfect square status and the type by perfect square status interaction were nonsignificant. People do not appear to speed comparison of natural number or radical expression pairs composed of perfect squares by automatically activating associated “tie” multiplication problems. However, there are two reasons to be cautious when interpreting this failed prediction. First, the distance, size, and type variables entered during the initial steps explained a large percentage of the variance in RTs. Little variability remained to be explained by the time the perfect square variables were entered. Second, although perfect squares may not be privileged on speeded tasks like magnitude comparison, they may benefit from special processing on unspeeded tasks like number line estimation and arithmetic problem-solving. For these reasons, we return to the second question with data from the NLE task.

Finally, we estimated RTs using the predictors from the equivalence strategy model separately for each participant. There was considerable variation between participants in the magnitudes of the β weights for the five predictors (Fig. 2). Later, these individual differences will be used to predict performance on the irrationals knowledge test.

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Fig. 2. Distributions of the β weights for the distance, size, type, perfect square, and type by perfect square interaction variables.

Number Line Estimation Task

Data from one participant were lost due to computer failure. Thus, the analyses included responses from 80 participants. Due to a programming error, 5.8% of the natural number trials were lost. These lost trials were random and did not affect the results. We trimmed outlier responses by discarding trials for which the RT was outside of the interval 1.5 – 15 sec (4.6% of the overall data). Our analyses focused on the second research question: Do people use anchoring strategies to facilitate performance?

Average absolute error, response time, and linearity. First, we analyzed average absolute error using a one-way ANOVA with type (natural numbers, one-digit radicals, perfect square radicals, and two-digit radicals) as the factor. See Fig. 3a. There was a main effect of type $F(3, 316) = 14.13, p < .001, \eta^2 = .118$. Post-hoc comparisons using Tukey's procedure found that average absolute error was comparable for natural numbers and perfect squares ($p = .836$). Error for these two number types was lower than for the one-digit radicals and two-digit radicals ($ps < .001$), which were comparable to each other ($p = .706$).

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Fig. 3. Average absolute error (a) and response times (b) on the number line estimation task revealed that, compared to natural numbers and perfect squares, one- and two-digit radicals were more difficult to process.

Next, we analyzed response time using a one-way ANOVA with type as a factor, finding a main effect $F(3, 316) = 27.95, p < .001, \eta^2 = .210$. See Fig. 3b. Post-hoc comparisons using Tukey's procedure revealed that natural numbers and perfect squares were estimated equally quickly ($p = .908$). Response time for these two number types was lower than for one-digit and

two-digit radicals ($ps < .001$). Finally, response times were lower for one-digit radicals than for two-digit radicals ($p < .001$).

How linear were participants' estimates for natural numbers, perfect squares, one-digit radicals, and two-digit radicals? For each of the four types, best-fitting lines predicting the selected position from the actual position were plotted (Fig. 4). Overall performance was high across all four blocks. For natural numbers and perfect squares, the R^2 values were both 1.00. For one-digit and two-digit radicals, the R^2 values were .97 and 1.00, respectively.

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Fig. 4. Number line estimation performance was highly linear on average.

These analyses concerned the overall accuracy of estimates. To examine whether averaging performance concealed individual differences, we repeated them separately for each participant, estimating the best-fitting lines for each of the four number types (Fig. 5). Estimates for natural numbers and perfect squares were highly linear across participants. By contrast, there was greater variation in the linearity of participants' estimates for one-digit radicals like and two-digit radicals like .

XXX

Fig. 5. Individual differences in the linearity of participants' estimates were greatest for two-digit radicals.

Estimation strategies. On the strategy questionnaire, participants self-reported the strategies they used for each block of the NLE task. After dropping illegible and incoherent responses, full data were available for 63 of 81 questionnaires. All 63 questionnaires were coded by the first author and a naïve volunteer. Interrater agreement, measured by Cohen's kappa,

averaged .74 across the eight prompts. Participants reported using multiple strategies, summarized in Table 3.

Table 3. Strategies self-reported on the number line estimation strategy questionnaire and their frequency of use.

Number Type	Strategy	% Use
Natural numbers	landmark of 0, 5, or 10	93.7
	other	6.3
Perfect squares	simplify & map	95.2
	other	4.8
One-digit radicals	single landmark – 1 perfect square	26.2
	double landmark – 2 perfect squares	43.7
	other – correct	19.0
	other – incorrect	7.9
Two-digit radicals	single landmark – 1 perfect square	25.4
	double landmark – 2 perfect squares	60.3
	other – correct	2.4
	other – incorrect	8.7

Given natural numbers, the most frequent strategy was to anchor on the nearby landmarks 0, 5, and 10, and to adjust slightly to the left or right (reported by 93.7% of participants). When estimating the position of the number 3, for instance, most participants found the midpoint (5) and then shifted their estimate slightly to the left. All additional strategies were categorized as *other* (6.3%). Given perfect squares like $\sqrt{9}$, most participants chose to simplify the expression to 3 and map it to the natural number line – the *simplify & map* strategy (95.2%). The use of this strategy, which is related to the equivalence strategy participants used for the MC task, suggests that perfect squares enjoy privileged processing for the NLE task. All other strategies were labeled *other* (4.8%).

Given one-digit and two-digit radicals, participants continued to anchor on nearby landmarks during estimation. In this case, however, the landmarks were perfect squares. This finding informs the second research question. Two strategies were observed; we illustrate them using $\sqrt{10}$ as an example. The *single landmark* strategy was to reason that $\sqrt{9} = 3$ and $\sqrt{16} = 4$, so estimate slightly to the left of 3. The *double landmark* strategy was to bound the estimate from both sides. One might reason that $\sqrt{4} = 2$, $\sqrt{9} = 3$, and $\sqrt{16} = 4$. Thus, one should estimate between 2 and 3. Participants were more likely to use the double anchor strategy than the single anchor strategy for unfamiliar two-digit radicals like $\sqrt{10}$ (60.3%) than for familiar one-digit radicals like $\sqrt{16}$ (40.7%). Correct, but rarely used strategies were categorized as “other – correct.” Vague, incorrect, or guess responses were categorized as “other – incorrect.”

Next, we evaluated whether the use of landmark strategies improved accuracy when estimating the locations of one-digit radicals ($\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{3}$) and two-digit radicals ($\sqrt{10}$ and $\sqrt{14}$). All four prompts were analyzed via one-way ANOVAs. The dependent measure was average absolute error and the factor was strategy – single landmark, double landmark, other-correct, and other-incorrect. See Table 4 for the results. For each prompt, there was a main effect of strategy ($F(3, 58) > 5.28, p < .001, \eta^2 > .215$). Post-hoc comparisons using Tukey’s procedure revealed that the single landmark and double landmark strategies were associated with the lowest average absolute errors. Landmark strategies were most beneficial for two-digit radicals. The average absolute errors were lower than the “other – correct” strategies. This is perhaps because the distances between one-digit radicals are lower than between two-digit radicals. For one-digit radicals like $\sqrt{2}$ and $\sqrt{3}$, the difference is about 1.4. Hence, multiple strategies can be used without compromising accuracy. In contrast, the difference between two-digit radicals like $\sqrt{10}$ and $\sqrt{14}$ is greater (about 4.5). For this reason, anchoring irrationals like $\sqrt{10}$ to perfect squares facilitated estimation considerably.

Table 4. ANOVA results evaluating whether different strategies on the NLE task are associated with average absolute errors.

Number Type	Prompt	$F(3, 58)$	p	η^2	Post-hoc strategy comparison ^s
One-digit radicals		5.28	< .001	.215	single landmark = double landmark = other – correct > other – incorrect
		10.02	< .001	.341	single landmark = double landmark = other – correct > other – incorrect
Two-digit radicals		14.66	< .001	.431	single landmark = double landmark > other – correct > other – incorrect
		9.96	< .001	.340	single landmark = double landmark > other – correct > other – incorrect

^a Computed by Tukey's procedure.

Irrationals Knowledge Test

All 81 participants completed a paper-and-pencil irrationals knowledge test composed of two sections – conceptual knowledge and procedural knowledge. These were in turn composed of five subsections – number classification, density knowledge, operation concepts, simple arithmetic, and complex arithmetic. Recall that Table 1 lists examples items from each subsection. Table 5 summarizes performance across all sections and subsections.

Table 5. Performance on all sections and subsections of the irrationals knowledge test.

Section	Subsection	Mean (%)	SD
Conceptual	Number classification	75.1	20.4
	Density knowledge	49.0	26.4
	Operation concepts	66.9	22.6
	<i>average</i>	<i>63.6</i>	<i>17.2</i>
Procedural	Simple arithmetic	61.0	27.0
	Complex arithmetic	35.8	35.2
	<i>average</i>	<i>48.4</i>	<i>29.3</i>

To determine the number of constructs being measured across these subsections, we conducted a principal components analysis using varimax rotation. The two procedural subsections loaded onto a single *procedural* factor (eigenvalue = 2.3, 46.0% of variance explained) and the three conceptual subsections loaded onto a single *conceptual* factor (eigenvalue = 1.1, 22.8% of variance explained).² Hence, subsequent analyses focused on average scores on the conceptual section and the procedural section.

To address the second research question, which concerns the use of anchoring strategies during arithmetic problem-solving, we coded the strategies used on the complex arithmetic subsection of the irrationals knowledge test. Interrater agreement, measured by Cohen's kappa, was .95. We focused on whether participants used inefficient or efficient strategies.

The inefficient *prime factorization strategy* was used by only 12% of participants. It involves solving arithmetic problems by decomposing radicands into prime factors and then shifting pairs of common factors outside the radical sign. See Table 6 for an example. By contrast, 40% of participants used the *perfect squares factorization strategy*. It involves directly identifying the largest perfect squares factors of the radicand. This chunking strategy enabled them to solve problems using fewer operations (Table 6).

Table 6. Strategy use on the complex arithmetic subsection of the irrationals knowledge test.

Strategy	Example	Use (%)
Prime Factorization	= = = = = = = = =	12
Perfect Squares Factorization	= =	40

² See Fig. S1 of the supplementary materials for a plot of the two factors.

= =
= =

To evaluate whether arithmetic strategy use affected participants' procedural scores on the irrationals knowledge test, a one-way ANOVA was conducted. The strategy factor had four levels: prime factorization, perfect squares factorization, both strategies, and other. The category "other" refers to participants who used incorrect strategies or guessed. There was a main effect of strategy on procedural scores ($F(3, 76) = 51.59, p < .001, \eta^2 = .671$). Post-hoc comparisons with Tukey's procedure revealed that procedural scores were comparable between participants who used the prime factorization strategy and those who used the perfect squares factorization strategy ($p = .455$). The only significant score differences were between participants who used "other" strategies and those who used using the remaining strategies ($ps < .001$). Although the use of the perfect squares strategy is not associated with higher accuracy on complex arithmetic problems than the use of the prime factorization strategy, it may reduce processing time and working memory demand. We could not test this possibility because we did not measure these dependent variables.

Predicting Individual Differences in Knowledge of Irrationals

Recall that the third research question concerned whether individual differences in the magnitude representation and strategic processing of radical expressions predicts conceptual and procedural knowledge of irrationals. To answer this question, we extracted two sets of predictor variables from each participant, as described above. The first set consisted of the β weights for the three significant variables when predicting response times on the magnitude comparison task (distance, size, and type). The β weights for the distance and size variables index the precision of

magnitude representations and are common predictors of mathematical achievement in children (De Smedt et al., 2009). The β weight for the type variable indicates the additional time required to compare radical expressions versus natural numbers. In other words, it reflects the time needed to apply the equivalence strategy. The second set of predictor variables were the average absolute errors when estimating the positions of one-digit radicals and two-digit radicals on the NLE task. These variables reflect the efficiency of anchoring to neighboring perfect squares. The magnitude comparison variables were entered first and the NLE variables were entered second in hierarchical linear regressions predicting accuracy on the conceptual section and the procedural section.

For the conceptual knowledge measure, the magnitude comparison variables added during the first step were nonsignificant ($R^2 = .074$, $F(3, 76) = 2.02$, $p = .119$). Adding the NLE variables during the second step accounted for significant additional variance ($\Delta R^2 = .115$, $R^2 = .188$, $F(2, 74) = 5.23$, $p = .007$). In the final model, shown in Table 7, only the magnitude comparison variable type and the NLE variable two-digit radicals were significant predictors ($ps < .05$).

Table 7. Final models predicting conceptual and procedural knowledge of irrationals.

Measure	Predictor	<i>Std. β</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>p</i>	<i>R</i> ²
Conceptual Knowledge	Constant		11.87	.000	.188
	MC – β Distance	.039	.271	.788	
	MC – β Size	.053	.370	.712	
	MC – β Type	.235	2.21	.030	
	NLE 1D Radicals	-.022	-.184	.855	
Procedural Knowledge	NLE 2D Radicals	-.355	-2.97	.004	.322
	Constant		8.28	.000	
	MC – β Distance	.125	.945	.348	
	MC – β Size	-.045	-.343	.732	
	MC – β Type	.151	1.55	.125	

NLE 1D Radicals	-.104	-.952	.344
NLE 2D Radicals	-.411	-3.76	.000

For the procedural knowledge measure, the magnitude comparison variables accounted for significant variance in step 1 ($R^2 = .140$, $F(3, 76) = 4.14$, $p = .009$), and the NLE variables for significant additional variance in step 2 ($\Delta R^2 = .182$, $R^2 = .322$, $F(2, 74) = 9.91$, $p < .001$). In the final model, only the NLE variable two-digit radicals was significant (Table 7).

These findings inform the second and third research questions. With respect to the second research question, participants' ability to estimate the spatial locations of two-digit radicals (all irrational numbers) predicted conceptual and procedural scores. This indicates that strategically anchoring irrational numbers to perfect squares is crucial for succeeding on higher level tests of mathematical knowledge. Concerning the third research question, neither the distance nor the size variables from the magnitude comparison task predicted knowledge of irrationals in the final models. This suggests that although magnitude representations are significant predictors of RTs in the speeded magnitude comparison task, they are less important when predicting performance on unspeeded tasks measuring higher-level mathematical knowledge. Further, the significance of the magnitude comparison variable type for predicting conceptual scores supports the role of the equivalence strategy. Understanding when judgments of irrational numbers can and cannot be simplified to judgments of natural numbers depends on conceptual knowledge of number systems.

Discussion

Summary

To study how people understand highly abstract mathematical concepts, we used irrational numbers as a test case. Specifically, we addressed three research questions. The first asked whether radical expressions are compared solely by referencing a mental number line or using the equivalence strategy. We addressed this question by fitting two models to the magnitude comparison RT data. The first model, consistent with the equivalence strategy, defined the distance and size variables by the radicands' magnitudes. The second model, consistent with the mental number line strategy, defined the distance and size variables by the actual magnitudes of the radical expressions. The equivalence strategy model fit the data best. The type variable, which indicates whether the stimuli being compared are natural numbers or radical expressions, was a significant predictor above and beyond the distance and size variables. Collectively, these MC results suggest that people compare radical expressions by anchoring them on natural numbers.

The second research question asked whether people anchor their understanding of abstract irrational numbers to concrete natural numbers and perfect squares. Examples of such anchoring, besides the equivalence strategy, are evident on the NLE task. Strategy self-reports suggest that people anchor their estimates of one-digit and two-digit irrationals to nearby perfect squares – the single and double landmark strategies. Anchoring strategies were also observed on the complex arithmetic subsection of the irrationals knowledge test. When simplifying radical expressions, 40% of participants factored radicands into perfect squares, a more efficient strategy than the prime factorization strategy used by 12% of participants.

The third research question asked whether individual differences in the speed and accuracy with which irrational numbers are processed on the simple MC and NLE tasks predicts performance on measures of higher-level conceptual and procedural knowledge comparable to

classroom mathematics tests. The type variable for the magnitude comparison task, which indicates whether the stimuli are natural numbers or radical expressions, was a significant predictor of conceptual knowledge. We interpret this as reflecting the importance of selectively accessing the natural number components of radical expressions (i.e., radicands and roots) when reasoning about irrationals. Accuracy with two-digit radicals on the NLE task was a significant predictor of both conceptual and procedural knowledge. This reflects the cognitive value of anchoring irrational numbers to perfect squares. Nevertheless, we note that most of the variation in conceptual and procedural knowledge of irrational numbers was left unexplained. More generally, magnitude representations are necessary for arithmetic competence, but not to the same extent as for natural numbers, integers, and rational numbers. The role of magnitude representations seems to attenuate as the abstraction of number systems increases. Hence, alternative mechanisms must be invoked to explain arithmetic expertise with irrationals.

Theoretical Implications – Formal Anchoring Hypothesis

Dominant accounts of numerical and arithmetic development emphasize the recruitment, repurposing, and refinement of perceptuo-motor and visuospatial systems (Blair, Tsang, & Schwartz, 2013; Landy, Allen, & Zednik, 2014; Siegler, 2016). Based on our results that natural numbers and perfect squares support an understanding of the irrationals on a range of tasks, we hypothesize that abstract mathematical concepts are understood by selectively recruiting mathematical representations that align with task demands, a process we call *formal anchoring*. Our hypothesis builds on broader evidence of the use of anchors in decision-making, landmarks in spatial navigation, and reference points on a range of tasks (Holyoak & Mah, 1982; Rosch, 1975; Siegler & Thompson, 2014).

Mathematical tasks like magnitude comparison, number line estimation, and arithmetic problem-solving can impose high computational demands on limited cognitive resources. Formal anchoring efficiently alleviates these demands in task-specific ways. Magnitude comparison with radical expressions, for instance, can be performed using an informal “guess and check” algorithm to determine the greater or lesser value in number pairs like $(\sqrt{49}, \sqrt{16})$. Instead, people use the more efficient equivalence strategy. Radical expression pairs are interpreted as natural number pairs like $(7, 4)$ because the judgments are the same in both cases. On the NLE task, the computational demands of estimating the positions of one-digit and two-digit radicals are also high. People handle these demands by anchoring their estimates on neighboring perfect squares – the single and double landmark strategies. Arithmetic problem-solving on the irrationals knowledge test also benefitted from formal anchoring. Expressions like $\sqrt{100}$ can be simplified laboriously via prime factorization:

or more efficiently via perfect square factorization

A key feature of formal anchors is that they are task-specific. During NLE and arithmetic problem solving, perfect squares anchored people’s understanding of irrationals. On the magnitude comparison task, however, the appropriate anchors were natural numbers. To explain why particular concrete mathematical concepts are appropriate on some tasks but not others, it is useful to focus on the alignment between what a task demands and what a representation provides. An appropriate representation simplifies a task without altering its underlying nature. By doing so, the representation minimizes computational demands and optimizes performance.

Formal anchoring also results in differential performance gains depending on the task to be performed. For MC and NLE, it is highly beneficial for answering quickly and accurately. As discussed earlier, the use of anchoring strategies on NLE improved participants' accuracy for irrational numbers. In contrast, anchoring to perfect squares during arithmetic problem-solving was not associated with higher accuracy. The benefits afforded in this context are likely to be more modest and restricted to speed.

Formal Anchoring Varies Across Number Systems and Tasks

Our formal anchoring hypothesis may unify a constellation of seemingly disparate phenomena in the mathematical cognition literature. Here, we consider examples that apply to natural numbers, integers, rationals, and irrationals (Table 8).

For natural numbers, formal anchoring strategies are not needed because the comparison of one-digit numbers is directly supported by magnitude representations (Moyer & Landauer, 1967). In contrast, number line estimation with one-digit numbers is performed by referring to the midpoint 5 and the endpoints 0 and 10 (Barth & Paladino, 2011; Opfer et al., 2016; Siegler & Thompson, 2014). Further, natural number arithmetic can be supported by anchoring to 10, as when the problem $9 + 8$ is solved by decomposition: $9 + 8 = 9 + (1 + 7) = (9 + 1) + 7 = 10 + 7 = 17$ (Baroody, Purpura, Eiland, Reid, & Paliwal, 2015). Comparisons of multi-digit numbers are anchored to intervening multiples of 10 (Brysbaert, 1995; Franklin, Jonides, & Smith, 2009). When estimating the positions of multi-digit natural numbers, midpoint and endpoint landmarks are also referenced (Dotan & Dehaene, 2013; Peeters, Verschaffel, & Luwel, 2017). For arithmetic with multi-digit numbers, the anchors are often multiples of 10, as when $49 + 38$ is transformed to $50 + 37$ (Torbeyns, de Smedt, Ghesquiere, & Verschaffel, 2009).

Evidence for the use of anchoring strategies extends to more abstract number systems. For integers, zero is often used as a cognitive anchor when performing magnitude comparison, number line estimation, line bisection, and arithmetic computations (Gullick & Wolford, 2013; Tsang et al., 2015; Tsang & Schwartz, 2009; Varma & Schwartz, 2011). Fractions are often processed in relation to unit fractions like $\frac{1}{2}$ when engaging in magnitude comparison and number line estimation judgments (Fazio et al., 2016; Siegler & Thompson, 2014). When rational numbers are expressed as decimal proportions, their magnitudes are anchored to natural numbers (Varma & Karl, 2013). During number line estimation with decimals, quartiles like .25 and tenths like .10 are anchored upon (Houseworth, 2016).

Table 8. A sample of formal anchors used across number systems and tasks.

	Naturals		Integers	Rationals		Irrationals
	one-digit	multi-digit		fractions	decimals	
Magnitude Comparison	none	multiples of 10	0	unit fractions, decimals	naturals	naturals ^a
Number Line Estimation	0, 5, 10	quartiles thirds	0	unit fractions, decimals	quartiles tenths	perfect squares ^b
Arithmetic Computation	10	multiples of 10	0	?	?	perfect squares ^c

^a Supported by the equivalence strategy on the MC task.

^b Supported the single and double landmark strategies on the NLE task.

^c Supported by the perfect squares factorization strategy on the irrational knowledge test.

Instructional Implications

Our results have three potential implications for instructional design in mathematics. First, performance patterns on the MC and NLE tasks suggest that most people represent the magnitudes of irrationals accurately. Nonetheless, some people placed irrationals on the number line haphazardly. Drawing on the cognitive science literature on learning and instruction

(Schwartz & Bransford, 1998), we recommend teaching the compression of the irrationals on the number line by contrasting their nonlinear spacing with the linear spacing of other numbers.

Students may benefit from explicit strategy instruction to estimate the values of irrational numbers by referencing perfect squares via the single and double landmark strategies.

The second pedagogical implication is based on strategy differences during arithmetic problem-solving. Participants who used the prime factorization strategy required more steps and likely spent more time on task. Those who used the perfect squares factorization strategy could skip steps by recognizing the perfect square factors under the radical signs. Not all learners discover such strategies on their own. Hence, the perfect squares factorization strategy should be taught during formal instruction. Doing so may improve the adaptive expertise of students, or their ability to recognize and apply optimal strategies (Hatano & Oura, 2003).

Third, it is worth noting that the correlation between magnitude knowledge and arithmetic expertise is weaker for irrationals than other number systems. Although interventions that improve magnitude knowledge result in greater arithmetic expertise for natural numbers, integers, and rational numbers (Fuchs et al., 2013; Siegler & Ramani, 2009; Tsang et al., 2015), similar learning gains may be unlikely for the irrationals. The individual differences analyses did not find a relationship between the precision of magnitude representations as measured by distance and size effects and conceptual and procedural knowledge of irrationals. We tentatively suggest a generalizable guideline for teaching highly abstract mathematical concepts like the irrationals. Instruction should focus on strategies for anchoring abstractions to task-appropriate formal concepts.

Conclusion

Most research in numerical cognition focuses on relatively concrete concepts like natural numbers, integers, and rational numbers. Our study of irrationals hints at how the mind grasps abstract mathematical concepts incapable of being directly perceived or fully grounded in visuospatial referents. We suggest that the numerical magnitudes and symbolic procedures associated with irrationals are understood by task-specific anchoring to natural numbers and perfect squares. Anchoring is a general cognitive mechanism that appears to be particularly crucial to mathematical cognition. Across a wide range of task types and number systems, it supports an intuitive understanding of otherwise foreign concepts. Of course, formal anchoring may only explain how mathematical concepts become meaningful in some contexts. The next step is to delineate the conditions under which it explains how other abstractions are discovered, comprehended, and best taught. Doing so will illuminate how the abstract becomes concrete.

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Figure Captions

Fig. 1. Distance and size effects, defined by the radicands and consistent with the equivalence strategy hypothesis, were found for natural number and radical expression magnitude comparisons. Shaded regions are 95% confidence envelopes.

Fig. 2. Distributions of the β weights for the distance, size, type, perfect square, and type by perfect square interaction variables.

Fig. 3. Average absolute error (a) and response times (b) on the number line estimation task revealed that, compared to natural numbers and perfect squares, one- and two-digit radicals were more difficult to process.

Fig. 4. Number line estimation performance was highly linear on average.

Fig. 5. Individual differences in the linearity of participants' estimates were greatest for two-digit radicals.